

SELF HELP GROUPS AS A CATALYST FOR WOMEN EMPOWERMENT

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ABSTRACT

Microfinance is emerging as a powerful tool for poverty alleviation in the new economy. In India, microfinance scene is dominated by Self Help Groups (SHGs) – Bank Linkage Programme aimed at providing a cost effective mechanism for providing financial services to the ‘unreached poor’. Based on the philosophy of peer pressure and group savings as collateral substitute, the SHG programme has been successful in not only in meeting peculiar needs of the rural poor, but also in strengthening collective self-help capacities of the poor at the local level, leading to their empowerment. The present study tries to analyse the importance of microfinance in poverty alleviation, rural development and enabler for women empowerment and to make comparative study of members and non-members of SHGs. The researchers have selected 50 members of SHGs and 50 non-members of SHGs from Moradabad city. The study uses Mann Whitney Test and mean scores to test the hypothesis. Findings from the study confirmed that microfinance has the ability to reduce poverty in its clients when the products given to clients were incorporated with training, supply of equipment and regular monitoring. The paper concludes that SHG is an effective instrument to empower women socially and economically which ultimately contributes in the overall development of the country like India wherein still large segment of women population are underprivileged, illiterate, exploited and deprived of basic rights of social and economic spectrum.

Key words: Self help Group, women empowerment, microfinance, entrepreneur

INTRODUCTION

Empowerment can be viewed as a means of creating a social environment in which one can take decisions and make choices either individually and collectively for social transformation. It strengthens innate ability by way of acquiring knowledge, power, and experience. In India women have been the vulnerable section of society and constitute a sizeable segment of the population. Women face gender specific barriers to access education, health, employment, etc. Microfinance deals with the women below poverty line.

Microfinance is emerging as a powerful tool for poverty alleviation in the new economy. In India, microfinance scene is dominated by Self Help Groups (SHGs) – Bank Linkage Programme aimed at providing a cost effective mechanism for providing financial services to the ‘unreached poor’. Based on the philosophy of peer pressure and group savings as collateral substitute, the SHG programme has been successful in not only in meeting peculiar needs of the rural poor, but also in strengthening collective self-help capacities of the poor at the local level, leading to their empowerment. Before 1990s credit schemes for rural women were almost negligible. The concepts of women’s credit were almost negligible. The concept of women’s credit was born on the insistence by women oriented studies that highlighted the discrimination and struggle of women in having the access of credit. However, there is a perceptible gap in financing genuine credit needs of the poor especially women in the rural sector.

In developing countries like India emphasis is being laid upon the development of women as an entrepreneur and their active participation in the development process of their country. Women can be successful and better entrepreneurs if given the much needed favourable environment and provided with enough resources most importantly the required amount of capital. The studies of rural women have proved their business excellence. They have been found to be better in credit utilisation than men but because of lack of access to assets they are often more vulnerable to poverty than males. Since the credit requirements of the rural poor cannot be adopted on project lending approach as it is in the case of organised sector, there emerged the need for an informal credit supply through SHGs. The rural poor with the assistance from NGSs have demonstrated their potential for self help to secure economic and financial strength. Various case studies show that there is a positive correlation between credit availability and women empowerment.

There are many successful women organisations working for the overall upliftment of the rural women like:

- Shri Mahila Griha Udyog Lijjat Papad
- Self Employed Women Association
- The Working Women Forum
- Rashtriya Mahila Kosh
- Mann Deshi Mahila Sahakari Bank Limited, etc.

Banking sector has also emerging in a big way to participate in the microfinance movement. At present many commercial banks are taking much interest in developing schemes exclusively for women. Various leading public and private sector banks have been providing finance under different schemes to the women entrepreneurs with a relief in interest rate on credit.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Muhammad Yunus (2004) traces the evolution of the ideas and practice of micro credit as pioneered by the Grameen Bank. Over the years micro credit programmes in Bangladesh have grown, providing a wide range of services to meet the economic and social needs of its citizens, mostly poor women. It comes up with suggestions regarding the emerging issues of financial self reliance and institutional of micro credit programmes.

An Arundhati Chattopadhyay (2005) point out that economic empowerment is a sine quo non for elevating the status of women in our society. One possible approach towards achieving this end could be through entrepreneurship development. Through entrepreneurship development a women will not only generate income for her but also generate employment for other women in the locality. This will have a multiplier effect in the generation of income and poverty alleviation.

Bentul Mawa (2008) conducted a research study focusing the issue under discussion and concluded that microfinance is an innovative step towards alleviating poverty. The author mentioned that microfinance facilities provided to the people help them to use and develop their skills and enable them to earn money through micro enterprises. Moreover provision of microfinance helps them to smooth their consumption level and manage unexpected risks. Microfinance helps the poor to built assets, educate their children and have a better quality of life. The study also suggests that this organisation needs to look more seriously at the diversified needs of the poor people and target the extremely poor.

Debotosh Sinha (2008) reported the experiences of women who set up businesses after joining SHGs. They had joined with their husbands in their business experienced considerable growth. A common constrained voiced by the women was insufficient training inputs and lack of institutional support. He suggested a need and local resource based training inputs to enable SHG members to take up suitable economic activities that are based on locally available raw material.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The present study aims at the following objectives:

- To analyse the importance of microfinance in poverty alleviation, rural development and enabler for women empowerment
- To make comparative study of members and non-members of SHGs

IMPORTANCE OF MICROFINANCE IN POVERTY ALLEVIATION, RURAL DEVELOPMENT AND ENABLER FOR WOMEN EMPOWERMENT

Microfinance is the provision of a broad range of financial services such as deposits, loans, payments, money transfers and insurance to the low income households and their micro enterprises, the basic purpose of microfinance is to provide access to financial assistance, including credit to the poor to enable them to start or expand micro enterprises to break out of poverty. Micro credit enables the poor people to be thrifty and helps them in availing the credit and other financial services for improving their income and living standards.

The importance of microfinance in poverty alleviation, rural development and enabler for women empowerment can be highlighted here in below:

- Microfinance increases the income and assets of the poor, thus it is one of the poverty reducing strategy.
- It provides financial education and credit establishment to low income entrepreneurs that cannot access traditional forms of credit.
- Many SHGs have come into existence with the help of banks and grants from government and they are helping others to build their own status.
- The microfinance has reduced the reliance of poor on the indigenous bankers.
- Microfinance institutions mobilize the savings and give returns to small investors.
- Microfinance allows clients to remain close to their homes, children, field, livestock and livelihood.
- When a women becomes a member of SHG, her sense of public participation, enlarged horizon of social activities, high self-esteem, self respect and fulfilment in life expands and enhances the quality of status of women as participants, decision makers and beneficiaries in the democratic, economic, social and cultural spheres of life
- Due to microfinance the income has increased and with increase in disposable income the education level and standard of living has amplified in the rural areas.
- It develops entrepreneurial spirit.
- It promotes gender equality and women empowerment
- It eradicates extreme poverty and hunger and thus raises the standard of living.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Type	: Empirical
Type of Sampling	: Convenience Sampling
Sampling Unit	: Women who are members and non-members of Self Help Groups
Sampling Universe	: Jaipur (Rajasthan) and Moradabad (Uttar Pradesh)
Sample size	: 50 women members of SHGs and 50 women non-members (Total 100)
Data Type	: Primary as well as Secondary Data
Data Source	: Survey through questionnaire
Tools	: Mann-Whitney Test and mean scores have been taken on a five point likert scale.

Scope of the study: The scope of study is related to women who are members of Self Help Groups in Jaipur (Rajasthan) and Moradabad (Uttar Pradesh). The scope of the research shall be in reliance with the methods and instruments of research used in this study. Special attention has been given to carry out the research in a manner such that it contributes to the overall study micro finance and financial inclusion. Opinion of various experts in Jaipur and Moradabad has been taken about the working of SHGs. Their views have been incorporated in this paper. The paper also takes the references of various articles written by various experts on .micro finance and financial inclusion.

The researchers identifies ten variables each based on literature representing difference aspects that could influence the standard of living of female members and non-members of SHGs.

Table 1: Various variables to be considered while determining the status of women

S. No.	Factors
1	Allowed to go outside for work and other matters
2	Personally own any property or valuables
3	Allowed to make independent savings
4	Ideas and opinions are being listened and entertain at home
5	Children goes to school regularly
6	Toilet facility available at home
7	Access to & Aware about Health Care
8	Improvement in decision making abilities in family decisions
9	Satisfied with improvement in social status
10	Access to & Awareness about Sanitation

SELF HELP GROUPS

Self Help Groups is a process by which a large group of women (10-20), with common objectives are facilitated to come together voluntarily to participate in the development activities such as saving, credit and income generation thereby ensuring economic independence. SHG phenomenon definitely brings group consciousness among women, sense of belongingness, adequate self confidence. In fact, what a women cannot achieve as an individual, can accomplish as a member of a group with sufficient understanding about her own rights, roles, privileges and responsibilities as a dignified member of society in par with man.

SHG is a small voluntary association to form a group. It is informal and homogenous group of not more than 20 members. SHGs consist of maximum 20 members because any group having more than 20 members has to be registered under Indian legal system. That is why it is recommended to be informal to keep them away from bureaucracy, corruption, unnecessary administrative expenditure and profit motive. In fact, it is a home grown model for poverty reduction which simultaneously works to empower and shape the lives of its members in a better way. Groups are expected to be homogenous so that the members do not have conflicting interest and all the members can participate freely without any fear. SHGs movement has triggered off a silent revolution in the rural credit delivery system in India. SHGs have proved as an effective medium for delivering credit to rural poor for their socio-economic empowerment.

The following SHGs were visited by researchers namely;

- Jagrukta
- Nai Kiran,
- Anmol

HYPOTHESIS

Researchers have framed 10 hypothesis. The details are mentioned herein below:

Hypothesis 1

H_{0a} There is no significant difference between member and non-members of SHGs regarding permission from the family to go outside for work and other matters.

Hypothesis 2

H_{0b} There is no significant difference between member and non-members of SHGs regarding personally owning property and valuables

Hypothesis 3

H_{0c} There is no significant difference between member and non-members of SHGs regarding making independent savings from earnings

Hypothesis 4

H_{0d} There is no significant difference between member and non-members of SHGs regarding their ideas and opinions are being listened and entertain at home

Hypothesis 5

H_{0e} There is no significant difference between member and non-members of SHGs regarding schooling of their children

Hypothesis 6

H_{0f} There is no significant difference between member and non-members of SHGs regarding facility of toilet at home.

Hypothesis 7

H_{0g} There is no significant difference between member and non-members of SHGs regarding access to & aware about health care

Hypothesis 8

H_{0h} There is no significant difference between member and non-members of SHGs regarding improvement in decision making abilities in family decisions

Hypothesis 9

H_{0i} There is no significant difference between member and non-members of SHGs regarding satisfaction with improvement in their social status within family as well as outside.

Hypothesis 10

H_{0j} There is no significant difference between member and non-members of SHGs regarding access to & awareness about sanitation

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Perception on the Concerns for the Ten Variables Relating to Standard of Living of Women

Opinion of respondents – For least 1 & for highest 5

Questions were asked from the respondents about the experience while working as members of Self Help Groups and non-members. The following data is obtained:

Table 2: Mean Score of Perceptions of respondents

S. No.	Variables	Female Members of SHGs	Non-Members
1	Allowed to go outside for work and other matters	4.02	2.52
2	Personally own any property or valuables	3.92	2.84
3	Allowed to make independent savings	4.02	2.82
4	Ideas and opinions are being listened and entertain at home	4.02	2.68

5	Children goes to school regularly	3.92	2.56
6	Facility of Toilet available at home	4.06	2.76
7	Access to & Aware about Health Care	4.06	2.52
8	Improvement in decision making abilities in family decisions	3.96	2.64
9	Satisfied with improvement in social status	4.24	2.44
10	Access to & Awareness about Sanitation	3.94	2.64

TESTING OF HYPOTHESIS

Mann-Whitney Test

- This test is the non-parametric equivalent of the independent *t-test*.
- Use either to test differences between two conditions in which different participants have been used.

The Table 3 summarizes the data after they have been ranked.

Table 3: Ranks

Variables		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Allowed to go outside for work and other matters	Members	50	71.30	3565.00
	Non-Members	50	29.70	1485.00
	Total	100		
Personally own any property or valuables	Members	50	70.04	3502.00
	Non-Members	50	30.96	1548.00
	Total	100		
Allowed to make independent savings	Members	50	69.48	3474.00
	Non-Members	50	31.52	1576.00
	Total	100		
Ideas and opinions are being listened and entertain at home	Members	50	70.74	3537.00
	Non-Members	50	30.26	1513.00
	Total	100		
Children goes to school regularly	Members	50	71.30	3565.00
	Non-Members	50	29.70	1485.00
	Total	100		
Toilet facility available at home	Members	50	73.94	3697.00
	Non-Members	50	27.06	1353.00
	Total	100		
Access to & Aware about Health Care	Members	50	72.80	3640.00
	Non-Members	50	28.20	1410.00
	Total	100		
Improvement in decision making abilities in family decisions	Members	50	69.04	3452.00
	Non-Members	50	31.96	1598.00
	Total	100		
Satisfied with improvement in social status	Members	50	72.31	3615.50
	Non-Members	50	28.69	1434.50
	Total	100		
Access to & Awareness about Sanitation	Members	50	69.55	3477.50
	Non-Members	50	31.45	1572.50
	Total	100		

The Table 4 provides the actual test statistics for the Mann–Whitney test, the Wilcoxon procedure and the corresponding z-score.

The significance value gives the two-tailed probability that a test statistic of at least that magnitude is a chance result, if the null hypothesis is true.

Table 4: Test Statistics

Test	Allowed to go outside for work and other matters	Personally own any property or valuables	Allowed to make independent savings	Ideas and opinions are being listened and entertained at home	Children go to school regularly	Toilet facility available at home	Access to & Awareness about Health Care	Improvement in decision making abilities in family decisions	Satisfied with improvement in social status	Access to & Awareness about Sanitation
Mann-Whitney U	210.00	273.00	301.00	238.00	210.00	78.00	135.00	323.00	159.50	297.50
Wilcoxon W	1485.00	1548.00	1576.00	1513.00	1485.00	1353.00	1410.0	1598.00	1434.50	1572.50
Z	-7.565	-7.481	-7.305	-7.468	-7.598	-8.713	-8.056	-6.969	-7.852	-7.130
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

The researchers have used Mann-Whitney Test and mean scores to test the above stated hypothesis

- The equation to convert a *z-score into the effect size estimate, r*, is as follows (from Rosenthal, 1991: 19):
 - *z* is the z-score that SPSS produces
 - *N* is the size of the study (i.e. the number of total observations)
 - We had 50 female members and 50 non-female members, so the total number of observations is 100.
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$$r = \frac{Z}{\sqrt{N}}$$

Table 5: Calculation of r Value

S. No.	Variables		r
1	Allowed to go outside for work and other matters	$r = \frac{-7.565}{\sqrt{100}}$	-0.756
2	Personally own any property or valuables	$r = \frac{-7.481}{\sqrt{100}}$	-0.748
3	Allowed to make independent savings	$r = \frac{-7.305}{\sqrt{100}}$	-0.730
4	Ideas and opinions are being listened and entertain at home	$r = \frac{-7.468}{\sqrt{100}}$	-0.746
5	Children goes to school regularly	$r = \frac{-7.598}{\sqrt{100}}$	-0.759
6	Facility of Toilet available at home	$r = \frac{-8.713}{\sqrt{100}}$	-0.871
7	Access to & Aware about Health Care	$r = \frac{-8.056}{\sqrt{100}}$	-0.805
8	Improvement in decision making abilities in family decisions	$r = \frac{-6.969}{\sqrt{100}}$	-0.696
9	Satisfied with improvement in social status	$r = \frac{-7.852}{\sqrt{100}}$	-0.785
10	Access to & Awareness about Sanitation	$r = \frac{-7.130}{\sqrt{100}}$	-0.713

Hypothesis 1

Female members (M = 4.02) were significantly in an advantageous position than non-members (M = 2.52), U = 210.00, z = -7.565, p < .005, r = -.756. Thus, Null hypothesis is rejected. There is a significant difference between member and non-members of SHGs regarding permission from the family to go outside for work and other matters.

Hypothesis 2

Female members (M = 3.92) were significantly in an advantageous position than non-members (M = 2.84), U = 273.00, z = -7.481, p < .005, r = -.748. Thus, Null hypothesis is rejected. There is a significant difference between member and non-members of SHGs personally owning property and valuables

Hypothesis 3

Female members (M = 4.02) were significantly in an advantageous position than non-members (M = 2.82), U = 301.00, z = -7.305, p < .005, r = -.730. Thus, Null hypothesis is rejected. There is a significant difference between member and non-members of SHGs regarding making independent savings from earnings they make.

Hypothesis 4

Female members (M = 4.02) were significantly in an advantageous position than non-members (M = 2.68), U = 238.00, z = -7.468, p < .005, r = -.746. Thus, Null hypothesis is rejected. There is a significant difference between member and non-members of SHGs regarding their ideas and opinions are being listened and entertain at home.

Hypothesis 5

Female members ($M = 3.92$) were significantly in an advantageous position than non-members ($M = 2.56$), $U = 210.00$, $z = -7.598$, $p < .005$, $r = -.759$. Thus, Null hypothesis is rejected. There is a significant difference between member and non-members of SHGs regarding schooling of their children.

Hypothesis 6

Female members ($M = 4.06$) were significantly in an advantageous position than non-members ($M = 2.76$), $U = 78.00$, $z = -8.713$, $p < .005$, $r = -.871$. Thus, Null hypothesis is rejected. There is a significant difference between member and non-members of SHGs regarding facility of toilet at home.

Hypothesis 7

Female members ($M = 4.06$) were significantly in an advantageous position than non-members ($M = 2.52$), $U = 135.00$, $z = -8.056$, $p < .005$, $r = -.805$. Thus, Null hypothesis is rejected. There is a significant difference between member and non-members of SHGs regarding access to & aware about health care.

Hypothesis 8

Female members ($M = 3.96$) were significantly in an advantageous position than non-members ($M = 2.64$), $U = 323.00$, $z = -6.969$, $p < .005$, $r = -.696$. Thus, Null hypothesis is rejected. There is a significant difference between member and non-members of SHGs regarding improvement in decision making abilities in family decisions

Hypothesis 9

Female members ($M = 4.24$) were significantly in an advantageous position than non-members ($M = 2.44$), $U = 159.50$, $z = -7.852$, $p < .005$, $r = -.785$. Thus, Null hypothesis is rejected. There is a significant difference between member and non-members of SHGs regarding satisfaction with improvement in their social status within family as well as outside.

Hypothesis 10

Female members ($M = 3.94$) were significantly in an advantageous position than non-members ($M = 2.64$), $U = 297.50$, $z = -7.130$, $p < .005$, $r = -.713$. Thus, Null hypothesis is rejected. There is a significant difference between member and non-members of SHGs regarding access to & awareness about sanitation.

FINDINGS OF THE PRESENT STUDY

The findings of the present study are mentioned herein below:

- 1) Members of SHGs are independent enough to work at home as well can go outside for work related activities. They are self reliant and there is no need to take any specific permission from family members while going outside. On the other hand, we found that non-members are not so at the advantageous position. They are leading a miserable life because their earnings are very less.
- 2) When members of SHGs are earnings handsome amount they can easily purchase property and other valuables from their savings. On the other hand, non members don't have such savings to purchase valuable things. As members have good earnings they can easily save the amount after meeting necessary expenses.
- 3) As members went outside for work and related activities, they are aware about various things so they generally give good ideas and opinions to other members of the family. Due to which even male family members are bound to accept their ideas and opinions.
- 4) The working members of SHGs are aware about the education of their children. They want their children to go to school and become good persons in future. Nearly all the members are sending their children to nearby schools. As they are earning so they do not find any problem

in giving the fees of their children. On the other hand, non members are not aware about the importance of education. Majority of non-members does not send their children to school. Also they do not have the means to pay the fees.

- 5) Now the government is focusing on the cleanliness of the areas. So the government is forcing the citizens to construct toilets and asking the people not to go outside. As members are earning good amount so they have constructed the toilets at home. While non members do not have the means to construct the toilets.
- 6) Members of SHGs are going outside for work; they see and listen about health care facilities. They are now aware about various health care facilities provided by the local government. So they have access to and are aware and concern about the health of their family members. While, non members do not have access to health care facilities as they are not aware about it.
- 7) As members of SHGs have new ideas and views, they generally give good suggestions to family members, thus there is an improvement in decision making abilities on important members.
- 8) As members of SHGs earn good amount of earnings, their standard of living increases in contrast to non members. Their status increases with in the family as well as in neighbouring areas.
- 9) Members are also aware about sanitation which is very important nowadays.

SUGGESTIONS

The researchers present the following suggestions, namely:

- 1) Although much progress has been made and the people who are already members of microfinance are satisfied with their overall development but the problem has not been solved yet, and the overwhelming majority of people who are living below poverty line, continue to have no practical access to formal finance sector. Microfinance institutions and NGOs must take the initiative to provide financial services to the doorsteps to 'unreached poor' who actually need the access to finance.
- 2) There are less programmes and schemes running in western UP as compared to the other states especially southern and eastern India. Hence people are not aware about the microfinance and its benefits. Government must take steps to reach the actual needy people and to spread awareness among the poor so that they can also take the benefit of microfinance.
- 3) There is an urgent need to streamline the procedure for applying, seeking and releasing of micro finance. The procedural difficulties are one of the major problems which have denied the needy groups, the financial benefits of the banks.
- 4) Women are economically and socially empowered after joining SHGs. But most of them are not aware of the trainings organised by the banks. The NGOs, regional rural banks and other commercial banks should actively take part in various trainings sessions provided to all women members wherein they can gain more knowledge about the various income generating activities.
- 5) Microfinance institutions have expanded the frontiers of institutional finance and have brought the poor, especially poor women into the formal financial system and enabled them to access credit and fight poverty. More research should be carried out to assess the impact of microfinance through SHGs. There should be more focus on socio-economic empowerment of members, social change, dynamics of groups, change in the standard of living, etc.

- 6) The factors responsible for poor performance of microfinance and functioning of SHGs should be investigated, examined and analysed scientifically and systematically to resolve the emerging problems, difficulties and challenges being faced.

IMPORTANCE AND NEED OF THE STUDY

The study was done to find out whether microfinance has positive impact on the clients or not by doing the comparative analysis between members and non-members clients. It was linked with their saving pattern employment and income, attitude and living standard and empowerment of women.

It is evident from the study that gender biasness is consistent. Women are not independent enough to take the decisions especially in the case of non-members because they are not much educated and less access to finance. Government must take initiative to create awareness among the people through various schemes and advertisements so that the unreached poor should take benefits of microfinance.

LIMITATIONS OF THE PRESENT STUDY

The limitations of the present study are mentioned herein below:

- 1) The study is confined to Moradabad city only.
- 2) Women empowerment depends on various factors. But we have taken only one factor 'self help groups' in this study.
- 3) The sample size in the study is restricted to 100 women members and non-members of self help groups.

CONCLUSION

When it comes to rural development, credit flows to the poor especially to the rural households, remained near to the ground. Through microfinance, loans are extended to borrower to allow them initiate a business, repair their houses, education of their children and improve the living condition of their families. When a woman becomes a member of SHG, her sense of public participation, enlarged horizon of social activities, high self-esteem, self respect and fulfilment in life expands and enhances the quality of status of women as participants, decision makers and beneficiaries in the democratic, economic, social and cultural spheres of life. In other words, we can say that SHG is an effective instrument to empower women socially and economically which ultimately contributes in the overall development of the country like India wherein still large segment of women population are underprivileged, illiterate, exploited and deprived of basic rights of social and economic spectrum. Findings from the study confirmed that microfinance has the ability to reduce poverty in its clients when the products given to clients were incorporated with training, supply of equipment and regular monitoring. Microfinance has the ability to increase income level, labour employment and improve standard of living.

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